

The Future of the World's Waters is Indigenous

Brazil, Latin American and the Caribbean are Indigenous lands! During the last centuries, Indigenous people have lost territories and rights over the world. These losses have impacted natural resources and the sustainability of Indigenous populations across continents.

The governance of these areas by Indigenous peoples is historically associated with high carbon storage, and greater biodiversity, ecosystem services and water quality (e.g., Fao & Filac, 2021). Therefore, the preservation of the rights of these people is critical to mitigate the consequences of climate change and maintain the quality of human life.

According to ECLAC (2014), there are currently 826 Indigenous peoples living in Latin American and the Caribbean, with a fragmented distribution over the landscape. These communities have managed the soils and waters for centuries, maintaining them in a sustainable way through ancient techniques and tools.

In 2020, the pandemic of COVID 19 exposed the fragility and invisibility of Indigenous peoples across continents. Considered one of the most vulnerable social groups in the world (Lustig & Tommasi, 2020), for Indigenous peoples, pandemics and diseases common in the past are a continuing threat due the absence of public policy and governmental support. Contagious diseases, invasions by mining, murders in several territorial disputes are only some of the threats faced by Indigenous peoples (Fig. 1). Recently, the world has seen the degradation of

the Yanomami peoples' health in the Brazilian Amazon, aggravated by government negligence.

One way to address the very important issue of health has been to invite medical students to Indigenous villages and participate in traditional rituals. Seeing firsthand is fundamental to breaking down prejudices and foster trust. This increases awareness of the role of future doctors in respecting traditional communities and their knowledge, while also providing Indigenous communities the opportunity to participate in public education. Poor health is also a result of their land's invasion, followed by the contamination of aquatic ecosystems by mercury and other heavy metals, deforestation and loss of resilience (Bouton *et al.*, 2022), and the potential reduction of the Amazon role as carbon sink (Gatti *et al.*, 2021).

Human pressures have changed the world and converted numerous natural ecosystems into unproductive areas. The Anthropocene age is characterized by human activity that has reached the highest indexes in our history and tipping points has become a reality in several ecosystems, indicating abrupt shifts and untold risks for natural resources (e.g., Dakos *et al.*, 2019). In this regard, Indigenous land along with cultural memory and identity represent a great advantage for biodiversity and ecosystem conservation. Indigenous peoples are the guardians of 22% of the world's areas, responsible for protecting approximately 80% of our biodiversity (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, [FAO](#)). According to FAO, indigenous people represent only 6% of the planet's population, with most living in middle-income countries and 19% associated with the extreme poor countries. This paradoxical condition is completely incompatible with the current biodiversity crisis and the role of the Indigenous knowledge in conservation of the landscapes.

In the face of crisis scenarios, Indigenous people need

Fig. 1 The mining murder and deforestation by Ibraim Nascimento, Afro-Brazilian visual artist and activist.

Fig. 2 Ibraim Nascimento and Minister of Indigenous People, Sônia Guajajara, in political manifestation against environmental devastation and violence against Indigenous peoples. Sônia Guajajara is the first Minister of Indigenous People in Brazilian history, and represents the historical fight of these people for rights and lands.

Fig. 3 *Victoria amazonica* in a floodplain on the Solimões River. Indigenous peoples' traditional management influences water quality and biodiversity conservation beyond their own lands (Photo by Bianca Weiss).

to become active participants in public politics involving the discussion of their rights and role in the preservation of their own territory. For the first time in history, the state of Alagoas has instituted the Superintendence of Policies for Indigenous Peoples. The Superintendence, which is part of the State Secretariat for Women and Human Rights (SEMUDH), will be headed by the second author, a Xucuru-Kariri Indigenous person, Maynami José Santana da Silva, from the municipality of Palmeira dos Índios. His role will be to build policies in favor of the traditional peoples of the State and to fight against social and racial inequalities. Under the present Brazilian government, mining in Indigenous lands and protected areas has been curtailed, and plans to combat deforestation in the Amazon and Cerrado biomes have been started (Fig. 2). The Brazilian Limnology Association, along with other scientific societies (e.g., the Brazilian Society for the Advancement of Science) and organizations, highlight the urgent need to support Indigenous peoples in land conservation. According to the United Nations, Indigenous people have a critical role in water preservation due their sustainable and traditional use and governance (UN, 2022). However, access to drinking water and proper sanitation is limited and often associated with the water pollution around Indigenous lands, absence of the projects and politics for Indigenous peoples and governmental insistence in denying Indigenous peoples' relevance when discussing water availability (UN, 2022).

Historically, their isolation, promoted by non-indigenous people, jeopardized their quality of life, spiritual values and culture and the sustainability of ecosystem services for future generations. The traditional use of landscapes represents a heritage for all, a rare indication that humans and biodiversity can coexist in a changing

world, thus avoiding abrupt shifts and turning points. In fact, Indigenous territories with full property rights saw a 66% reduction in annual deforestation compared with land outside their borders (Baragwanatha & Bayi, 2019). Many Indigenous peoples have a strict relationship with natural aquatic ecosystems, contributing to the preservation and sustainable use of aquatic biodiversity. Sometimes this connection with freshwater indicates a strong association with spiritual and cultural identity, reflecting knowledge about seasonal and hydrological cycles (Blackstock, 2001) and ancient management of these aquatic ecosystems, respecting aspects such as ecological resilience and sustained and responsible fishing. In Indigenous nations freshwater is often considered a gift, supporting ecosystem integrity and the dignity of the people as a symbol of sanctity and ancestors' presence (Fig. 3).

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Authors

VANESSA FE HA

Kankaing Indigenous People

Member of Young Limnologists Committee- 37th SIL Congress

Vanessa Fe ha is an indigenous Kaingang from the south of the Atlantic Forest, a journalist, academic and communications coordinator at Arpinsul and the Indigenous Knowledge Portal, and co-founder of the women's collective Ga Jare.

MAYNAMI JOSÉ SANTANA

Xucuru-Kariri Indigenous People

Superintendent of Policies for Indigenous Peoples of Alagoas State (Brazil)
Member of Scientific Committee- 37th SIL Congress

In addition to having a postgraduate degree in Law from Universidade Damásio de Jesus and being an activist for the cause of traditional peoples in Alagoas and Brazil, superintendent Maynami is a member of the legal advisory of the Articulation of Peoples and Indigenous Organizations of the Northeast, Minas Gerais and Espírito Santo (APOINME) and former president of the Indigenous Peoples Law Commission (3rd subsection of OAB-AL). He is considered the first indigenous person to work as a lawyer in Alagoas.

LUCIANA GOMES BARBOSA

Chair of 37th SIL Congress

Federal University of Paraíba (Brazil)

Luciana holds a Ph.D. (2009) in Ecology, Conservation and Wildlife Management from the Federal University of Minas Gerais. She is Associate Professor at the Federal University of Paraíba, and founder and coordinator of the International Drylands Limnology Network (INLD). Her research focuses on understanding the effects of drought and multiple stressors on biodiversity and resilience in dryland aquatic ecosystems. Luciana is President of the Brazilian Association of Limnology (ABLimno), Coordinator of the Environmental Working Group of the Brazilian Society for the Progress of Science (SBPC). Representative of the SBPC in the National Council for the Environment (CONAMA).

Fig. 4 Meeting of the Akroá Gamella people from Piauí and Maranhão (Brazil) concerning land demarcation.